

A Study on Ophthalmic Healthcare Services and Satisfaction with Eye Care Camps Organized in Rural Areas in Rajasthan

Ayushman Shukla¹, Dr. Ankit Sanjay Varshney²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Optometry, Sunrise University, Alwar (Raj.) India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Optometry, Sunrise University, Alwar (Raj.) India

ABSTRACT

Population growth is driving up demand for more affordable and high-quality health care in developing nations. However, the clients who receive these services have high expectations for the facilities. Providers of eye care attempt to meet their clients' needs on both a qualitative and quantitative level. The health care services have changed rapidly in the last ten years, particularly in the corporate level health care service providers, as a result of improved access to information and services, worries about affordability, and evolving proactive marketing practices for eye health care services. The goal of outreach initiatives for eye care should be to reach the unreached. Numerous healthcare facilities host community outreach programs to raise awareness, impart health knowledge, and offer potential medical assistance. To serve the great majority of the people, health care facilities must be extended to rural areas. Using a base hospital approach and planning outreach programs in rural areas are excellent ways to reach the underserved. The population will become more informed and receptive if the quality of care reaches a high level, which will greatly simplify the work of eye care professionals. In order to determine the parameters influencing the success of eye care camps held in rural Rajasthan, the current study was conducted. Blindness was also a thing in the prehistoric past. Since the dawn of humanity, various surgeons have treated blindness in even the wise

Keywords: Eye Care, Health Care Camps, Blindness, Hospitals, Rajasthan.

INTRODUCTION

A person's entire life may be adversely affected by visual impairment. Regrettably, blindness or reduced vision are common conditions in many regions of the world. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Agency for the Prevention of Blindness (IAPB), which has a global membership of corporations, professional associations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and eye care facilities, have created a global initiative to end preventable blindness by 2020 in light of this. Target activities for the "Vision 2020: The Right to Vision" program are divided into three main categories: infrastructure and human resource development, targeted illness control, and appropriate technology development. Lewallen and Courtright state that in order to meet the objectives of Vision 2020, significant programs pertaining to infrastructure, community outreach, and staff development will be required. The use of eye care services and their accessibility are essential to reaching Vision 2020's objectives. These suggest that in addition to hiring more people and building infrastructure, community initiatives are required to guarantee that eye care services are used.

The goal of outreach initiatives for eye care should be to reach the unreached. Numerous healthcare facilities host community outreach programs to raise awareness, impart health knowledge, and offer potential medical assistance. To serve the great majority of the people, health care facilities must be extended to rural areas. In India, the distribution of health care services is such that 80% are found in urban areas and 20% are found in rural areas; in contrast, the population distribution is roughly 20% urban and 80% rural. Using a base hospital approach and planning outreach programs in rural areas are excellent ways to reach the underserved. The population will become more informed and receptive if the quality of care reaches a high level, which will greatly simplify the work of eye care professionals.

Organizations in poor nations can make use of the resources they require by creating a core competency—widening access to a concentrated area of care. Organizations like 4Aravind, which provide specialized care, have made it simpler to standardize clinical and managerial procedures, develop a staff of paraprofessionals with specific training, pursue low-cost

technologies, and increase volume through targeted community outreach and education. The ability of the aforementioned firms to establish effective management systems that are impacted or supported by international partner organizations is a defining characteristic. Foundations and non-governmental organizations that fund human resources in the health care industry frequently prioritize developing clinical skills over administrative ones. When creating effective systems that can improve access to care, managerial expertise is equally as crucial as clinical expertise.

EYE CARE SCENARIO IN INDIA

The social and economic development of a country is inextricably linked to human development and health. The best asset a person may have is good health, which is necessary for one's moral, creative, intellectual, and spiritual growth. The greatest returns come from improved health, and social productivity depends on overall well-being. A thriving community provides the foundation for the construction of an economically sustainable society. The caliber of a society's population has a major impact on its progress. People's health must be protected and promoted in order to maintain social and economic progress. Prosperity and good health typically go hand in hand. Not only does India have to overcome a severe shortage of optometrists, but it also has to deal with the issue of avoidable visual impairment among its youth, particularly in rural areas. Out of the 125,000 optometrists required to serve the nation's population, there are only 45,000. According to Vinod Daniel, CEO of the India Vision Institute (IVI), this indicates that the nation lacks primary eye care due to a major impairment in early infancy screening.

FUNCTIONING OF EYE CARE CAMPS IN RURAL RAJASTHAN

Today, the key to any organization's success is its workforce, which is also its most valuable asset. The personnel is the true foundation of any firm, so we must invest in it. The revision of personnel policy, which addresses retirement benefit planning for human resources, is necessary to make our own employees happy. Only contented staff members can make a pleased customer. The foundation of quality is HRM. People in successful companies are seen as "internal customers" or "service partners." Important components of HRM are empowerment, continual training, and development. Consumerism has embraced health care. Patients are a category of customers who inquire and decide for themselves. They are searching for the best services at the best possible price, enquiring about available treatment alternatives, gathering additional details, demanding high-quality evidence, anticipating continuity of care, and investigating alternative therapies. When something is good, customers are happy. Customer focus is the cornerstone of quality. The key components of quality are continuity of care, accessibility, correctness, and speed of service. Two broad categories are used to describe the quality of healthcare: "clinical quality" and "quality service." Clinical quality criteria such as infection control, monitoring of complications, duration of stay, visual acuity, follow-up rate, and safe medication are among those that require ongoing monitoring and improvement. Standardized clinical protocols and managerial processes help to hone clinical skills. Several levels of maintenance need to be completed: Normal maintenance includes tasks like dusting and cleaning; preventive maintenance includes a schedule of planned maintenance actions completed by on-site maintenance personnel to stop equipment failures or breakdowns before they happen; scheduled maintenance is accomplished through agreements with outside specialized organizations; and equipment availability is ensured. Good customer service entails being kind and cordial. Consumers gauge quality using basic cues like contented expressions, the scent of clean linens, and overall hygienic conditions.

Outreach initiatives are crucial in underdeveloped nations when people lack access to healthcare and are unaware of health issues. School screening programs, community rehabilitation, and screening camps are a few of the often employed strategies. Planning, community involvement, ophthalmologists' involvement, standardization of systems and procedures, patient guidance, and review are essential components of outreach programs. Monitoring and evaluating performance and outcomes is crucial. To find out how the service may be enhanced, it is important to keep an eye on the quantity of camps, patients examined, patients recommended for surgery, and patients who have finished operations. The rate of acceptance is raised when free care is combined with food and transportation. Camp day operations require patients to be sent to the base hospital. Direct patient payment is another benefit of outreach program advertising for the hospital.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study's methodology is predicated on an appropriate and effective research design, which is mostly composed of the compilation of primary data, followed by data processing, statistical analysis, and report writing. Surveys have been the main method of gathering data for the study. A series of structured questionnaires specifically designed for the purpose were used.

Research purpose

The main goal of the current study was to thoroughly identify and investigate a number of factors that affect the efficacy of eye care camps held in rural Rajasthan, India.

Research Design

A research design is just the basic plan or framework that directs the researcher during data collection and analysis. The crucial first stage in collecting and analyzing the necessary data is research design, which also helps determine the study's location, sample size, population, and other factors. The current study was a cross-sectional, observational, community-based investigation designed to identify the variables influencing the success of eye care camps.

Research Population

Participants in the camp from all age groups living in rural areas made up the study population.

Sample Size

A total of 250 patients who were discovered through the eye health camp were chosen as a sample size from the list of patients in rural Rajasthan. The participants were chosen through the use of random sampling.

Inclusion Criteria:

All the participants in all age group attending the camp.

Exclusion Criteria:

Those not willing to participate in the study.

DATA ANALYSIS STRATEGY

SPSS 21.0 is used to thoroughly outline and investigate the data that was obtained from the polls. It enables accuracy and consistency in information and presents data in a way that supports these qualities, making it very easy to interpret the information that has been obtained. The measures from the ensuing inquiry were imported into SPSS for additional analysis. The information was described using descriptive statistics, and the relationship between the usage of eye care services and public awareness of eye illnesses was determined using the Pearson's chi-squared test in SPSS. In a well-structured questionnaire, descriptive statistics were employed to provide a clear image of background characteristics such as age, sex, and other variables. Both the independent and dependent variables' frequency distributions were employed. Pearson's chi square was used to measure and test the relationship between the variables. In every instance, a p-value less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant. The study variables, which included frequency, percentage, standard deviation, mean, and confidence interval, were utilized to summarize and present the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis Using Descriptive Statistics Of Statements Pertaining To The Degree Of Satisfaction With The Entire Camp Procedure

The opinion statements pertaining to the degree of satisfaction with the overall camp procedure are shown in the following table with descriptive statistics.

Descriptive Statistics		
	Mean	Std. Deviation
Are you satisfied with the way propagation done	4.94	.757
Happy with the waiting time in registration	4.83	.781
Approach of the receptionist in the registration place	4.91	.758
Time Taken in the consultation	5.11	.669
Counselling by the doctors	4.98	.728
Approach of the doctors	5.04	.708
Explanation given for ailment	5.04	.682
Approach of the camp counsellor	4.83	.707
Answering the queries	4.77	.774
Approach of the spectacle provider	4.82	.739
Approach of the camp medicine distributor	5.03	.674
Approach of the other support staff	4.98	.731
Approach of the volunteers	4.74	.792
Hospital staff	4.96	.663
Overall satisfaction	5.17	.818

Interpretation: The data above showed that most respondents were satisfied with the manner in which propagation was carried out, the length of time they had to wait to register, and the receptionist's approach at the registration desk. The length of time spent in consultation, the doctors' advice, their approach, An explanation of the illness, The camp counselor's approach, Responding to inquiries, The hospital staff, volunteers, the distributor of camp medications, the provider of spectacles, and other support staff members all made their approaches. They expressed satisfaction with the camp procedure as a whole. The table that follows provides descriptive statistics for the opinion comments regarding patients' satisfaction with hospital care after they are admitted from camp to the hospital for surgery.

Descriptive Statistics		
	Mean	Std. Deviation
Satisfaction on Registration process	4.89	.969
Satisfaction on the preoperative work	4.61	1.055
Satisfaction on the doctor' sex planation and counselling	4.74	1.030
Approach of the Nurses and paramedical staff	4.64	1.062
Availability of nurses and paramedical staff when inneed	4.64	.962
Satisfaction on the dietary service	4.76	.993
Happy with the infrastructure of the hospital	4.05	1.398
Happy with the service of the medical store	4.82	1.017
Follow Up services	4.90	.880
Happy with handing of any post-operative complications	4.21	1.145
Happy with Extent of restoration of sight	4.05	1.398

Interpretation: The aforementioned data showed that most respondents were satisfied with the following: the registration process; preoperative work; the doctor's explanation and counseling; the approach taken by nurses and paramedical staff; the availability of these personnel when needed; the dietary service; the medical store's service; and the follow-up services provided once they arrived at the hospital for surgical intervention.

The descriptive statistics for the opinion statements regarding the main issues hospital patients experience are shown in the following table.

Descriptive Statistics			First fiveRank for major problems
	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Communication and Language	2.56	1.012	2
Procedural formalities	2.72	1.046	3
Waiting time	3.13	.902	-
Lack of staff attention	3.10	.901	-
Lack of infrastructural facilities	3.02	.836	-
Accessibility	3.21	.868	-
Lack of personal care	2.85	.903	4
Level of cleanliness in the hospital	2.05	1.396	1
Quality of food	2.86	.870	5

Interpretation: Based on the data above, it was found that most respondents were content with the language and the staff's ability to communicate at these programs. In general, they also felt at ease with the formality of the procedure. Regarding the waiting period, they were satisfied with it.

They thought that the staff's attentiveness was good. They thought these appropriate when they were questioned about the infrastructure. For the most part, they had little trouble getting to these facilities in the camps. The high caliber of the cuisine and the attentive service made them feel happy and satisfied.

Cross Tabulation analysis between selected factors for mean scores

The cross-tabulation of patient satisfaction, hospital care services, significant problem areas, and age is shown in the following table.

Age		Satisfaction	Satisfaction of Patients on Hospital Care Service	Major Problem
0-20	Mean	3.9833	3.5325	3.9325
	Std. Deviation	4.9479	.57958	.52582
21-40	Mean	3.8354	3.4148	3.6840
	Std. Deviation	.67754	.69193	.67857
41-60	Mean	3.9487	3.5985	3.8305
	Std. Deviation	.64581	.64962	.62544
61-80	Mean	3.9422	3.5450	3.8263
	Std. Deviation	.63333	.64848	.63042
>80	Mean	4.0508	3.8312	3.9788
	Std. Deviation	.70990	.62011	.62915
Total	Mean	3.9453	3.5735	3.8316
	Std. Deviation	.63724	.64850	.62568

Interpretation: Participants between the ages of 0 and 20 expressed greater satisfaction with the camp's general procedure, with issues raised by hospital patients and hospital care services coming in second. Age-group respondents (21–40 years old) expressed a moderate level of satisfaction with hospital care services. This age group's respondents were found to be the most content with the camp's overall procedure when compared to the issues hospital patients faced. The problem areas faced by hospitalized patients and hospital care services were found to be of greater satisfaction with respondents from the age groups of 41-60 and 61-80 years, respectively, than with the entire camp process. The respondents who were above 80 years old had the highest level of satisfaction with the overall camp procedure.

The cross-tabulation of patient satisfaction with hospital care services, major problem areas, and gender is shown in the following table.

Sex		Satisfaction	Satisfaction of Patients on Hospital Care Service	Major Problem
Male	Mean	3.9147	3.5200	3.7869
	Std. Deviation	.63692	.64518	.63013
Female	Mean	3.9840	3.6409	3.8879
	Std. Deviation	.63698	.64784	.61682
Total	Mean	3.9453	3.5735	3.8316
	Std. Deviation	.63724	.64850	.62568

Interpretation: When it came to the overall camp process, hospital care services, and issues that patients in the hospital experienced, female respondents were found to be more satisfied than male respondents. When comparing the whole camp experience to medical care services and issues they encountered there, male respondents were found to be the most satisfied. When compared to the issues they encountered in the hospital and hospital care services, female respondents expressed the highest level of satisfaction with the camp's entire procedure.

CONCLUSION

In order to reach and accommodate those who are unable to visit the service headquarters for treatment, outreach camps are an alternative arrangement created by service providers. The outreach camps likewise aim to cover a larger population and offer services to a larger number of community members using the same infrastructure as the eye hospital or non-profit organization. An outreach camp is a means of promoting the hospital and raising awareness of the organization. It guarantees that the neighborhood will remember it and go there to conduct additional research. Outreach programs are helpful in building the hospital's reputation and branding. Outreach programs are effective in persuading and converting the local population to the importance of eye care. Due to the widespread perception that eye care is unselfish, altruistic, and advantageous for everyone, it is the greatest way to enter a society. Outreach programs assist service providers in gaining long-term advantages from the community, such as financial support, resources for buildings and infrastructure, food, and other items, as well as advocacy for the cause. Instead of waiting for the community to come to their hospital, a number of nations, including China, have adopted the strategy of training barefoot doctors who roam the neighborhood. This is the path to "Sarvodaya," which is the elevation of everyone, especially the underprivileged, oppressed, and service-deprived.

These individuals, whose low immunity and susceptibility to infections stem from their line of work, are unable to access hospitals because they cannot afford to lose a day's pay. Second, due to their own health and dependency circumstances as well as a lack of transportation options, women, children, and the elderly are unable to visit hospitals independently. They can't afford the facilities, even if they are provided. A hospital or non-profit organization might like to tally the number of individuals they have served because that is one measure of success from an economic standpoint. Hospital and outpatient department foot traffic cannot guarantee a high caseload. Hospitals must therefore use the outreach camp strategy in order to increase caseload. A comparable idea is represented by the way community ophthalmology or eye camps are conducted nowadays. The Community Eye Care Management Approach encompasses the adjustment of all variables influencing the state of eye health in both the community and the individual. It attempts to treat eye diseases at every stage of development. The area of concern grows as the focus moves from the individual to the community. This will address the environmental and lifestyle factors that contribute to the illness process, concentrate on the problems and requirements of the community, and improve prioritizing. Programmatic and analytical techniques could be used to diagnose the community in this way. Thus, the purpose of this micro-level research conducted in rural areas is to determine the epidemiological characteristics that influence the degree of acceptance of cataract therapy that is provided at no cost by a local non-profit health organization. which are based on the in-depth micro level survey and unofficial conversations with locals, will help patients respond more favorably to the eradication of blindness.

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